

Bayesian Optimal Sensor Placement for Parameter Estimation under Modeling and Input Uncertainties

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Abstract

A Bayesian optimal sensor placement (OSP) framework for parameter estimation in nonlinear structural dynamics models is proposed, based on maximizing a utility function built from appropriate measures of information contained in the input-output response time history data. The information gain is quantified using Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL-div) between the prior and posterior distribution of the model parameters. The design variables may include the type and location of sensors. Asymptotic approximations, valid for large number of data, provide valuable insight into the measure of information. Robustness to uncertainties in nuisance (non-updatable) parameters associated with modeling and excitation uncertainties is considered by maximizing the expected information gain over all possible values of the nuisance parameters. In particular, the framework handles the case where the excitation time history is measured by installed sensors but remains unknown at the experimental design phase. Introducing stochastic excitation models, the expected information gain is taken over the large number of uncertain parameters used to model the random variability in the input time histories. Monte Carlo or sparse grid methods estimate the multidimensional probability integrals arising in the formulation. Heuristic algorithms are used to solve the optimization problem. The effectiveness of the method is demonstrated for a multi-degree of freedom (DOF) spring-mass chain system with restoring elements that exhibit hysteretic nonlinearities.

Keywords: Bayesian learning; Optimal experimental design; Information entropy; Kullback-Leibler divergence; Structural dynamics; Nonlinear models

1. Introduction

Experimental data are used to inform a digital twin of a system operating under various conditions, selecting models of system components, estimating model parameters, improving virtual sensing capabilities and model-based predictions of important output quantities of interest (QoI). Combining data with models of systems are crucial in making decisions regarding performance, structural health, safety and maintenance. Optimally designed experiments and sensor systems provide substantial benefits to update models and model-based predictions and to support decisions in many fields of science, health and engineering, as well as to reduce cost of experimentation, instrumentation, or monitoring. By designing an optimal experimental set-up, it is possible to cost-effectively improve structural models, narrow the uncertainties in the model parameters and the model-based predictions of output QoI. A recent review of optimal sensor placement (OSP) strategies is covered in [1].

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Information theoretic-based approaches provide useful measures of the information contained in the data collected by a sensor configuration for estimating the model parameters. Past OSP approaches for parameter estimation have used measures of information such as Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) [2–6], information entropy [7–11], joint entropy [12, 13], KL-div [14–17], mutual information [18, 19] and value of information [20–22]. The aforementioned information-theoretic OSP techniques address parameter estimation of linear models of structures subjected to known inputs [8–11, 18, 23]. Such studies cover applications to model updating [7, 24], modal identification [19, 25, 26], model selection [27], structural health monitoring and damage detection [16, 28–30]. OSP for parameter estimation under unknown input can be found in [31] using spectral estimators. Information theoretic measures have also been introduced to measure the information gain for the purpose of response reconstruction for the case of known input [32, 33] as well as the case of output-only vibration measurements [34, 35] for linear models of structures. The response reconstruction under unknown input is carried out using Bayesian modal expansion techniques [34–37] and/or filtering techniques [38, 39].

These studies have mostly concentrated on linear models of structural dynamics. Limited studies are available for OSP for parameter estimation of nonlinear models based on information theoretic approaches. Information entropy and mutual information are used to design the optimal locations of sensors for parameter estimation of nonlinear suspension models of vehicles [40], nonlinear elastic models [41] and nonlinear hysteretic laws in finite element models of civil infrastructure [42]. For nonlinear models, an issue that is also related to OSP is the optimal design of actuator configuration (location and number of actuators) and the optimal design of input characteristics (frequency and amplitude content) so that the model nonlinearities are sufficiently activated, and thus the parameters related to model nonlinearities can be inferred from the measured data. The information entropy based approach introduced in [7] was used for the design of optimal input characteristics for linear and nonlinear suspension models of vehicles in [40].

In this work, the problem of optimizing the sensor configuration (type, number and location of sensors) is investigated for reliable parameter estimation of nonlinear models under modeling and input uncertainties. It is assumed that the excitation time histories and the response time histories at the sensor locations are measured. The OSP problem is addressed using information theoretic-based approaches. Such approaches include sampling [14] and asymptotic techniques [7]. In particular, asymptotic approximations, valid for large number of data, were demonstrated to provide useful insight into the measure of the information [7, 23, 43, 44] from a sensor configuration and it is the preferred techniques used in the present study. Past studies on OSP for parameter estimation using input-output vibration measurements assume that the input is available at the experimental design phase (e.g. [7, 23, 40–42]). This is the case of special types of laboratory experiments where one can partially control the input or the case of full-scale experiments performed on civil infrastructure using actuators where the input can also be partially controlled. However, there are a number of laboratory cases and physical phenomena (e.g. earthquakes), where the excitation is measured using sensors but is partially or completely unknown during the experimental design phase. As a result, the OSP should take into account the input uncertainty.

This study is mainly focused on nonlinear models of systems. The purpose is twofold. First, the modeling and input uncertainties are taken into account in the design of the OSP. Modeling uncertainties are associated with non-updatable (nuisance) parameters whose values are uncertain. Such uncertainties can be quantified by assigning a prior probability distribution function (PDF) and included in the formulation for OSP by generalizing the definition of the information gain so that such uncertainties are taken into account in the design. This work also addresses for the first time the uncertainty of the input response time history in the OSP design. Input uncertainties are associated

with the fact that the sensor system installed in a structure is designed to measure the time history of the excitation(s) when it occurs, but such measurements are not available at the experimental design phase. An example includes laboratory experiments carried out under broadband excitation, usually performed by applying a white noise excitation. One cannot usually control the details of the time history of the excitation or the excitation characteristics (intensity, frequency content) generated from the actuator. Moreover, multiple laboratory experiments are carried out to evaluate the structural characteristics under different uncertain realizations of the input time history, different excitation intensities and characteristics as well as various excitation locations, constituting the uncertain factors that should be taken into account in design of the OSP to be robust to uncertainties or variabilities expected in excitation location, amplitude and frequency characteristics as well as input time history details. Another application is on earthquake excited civil infrastructure (e.g. building, bridges) where sensors (mainly acceleration sensors) are installed to measure the excitation(s) at the base(s) of the structure. However, such excitation is unavailable during the experimental design phase. OSP design should take into account such uncertainties. Stochastic processed/fields can be used to model the variability in ground motion. For example, such variability can be described by simplified ground motion models (e.g. [45, 46]) and seismological models [47] used in the past to represent the ground motion by a large number of random parameters [48, 49]. The input can then be obtained as a specific realization of the underlining stochastic process, and the OSP should account for all such input realizations.

The presentation is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces briefly the Bayesian inference formulation for parameter estimation. The formulation is used in Section 3 to introduce the utility function built from the information gain quantified by the KL-div between the prior and posterior distribution of the model parameters to be inferred. The information gain is generalized to account for uncertainties in nuisance (non-inferred) parameters associated with model and input uncertainties. The high computational cost and storage requirements associated with the proposed framework are pointed out and computational issues for carrying out the OSP under model and input uncertainties are also addressed. The application of the proposed methodology in a spring-mass chain model of Bouc-Wen nonlinear hysteretic restoring force introduced to represent various systems, including a high-rise building excited by stochastic earthquake excitation models, is presented in Section 4. Numerical results demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the methodology. Concluding remarks are drawn in Section 5.

2. Bayesian Inference for Parameter Estimation

Consider a parameterized structural model and let $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ be the model parameters to be estimated using a set of data $\mathbf{D} = \{\mathbf{y}_\delta(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}, \mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}, k = 1, \dots, n_d\}$, where $\mathbf{y}_\delta(k)$ is the data of n_y output quantities (acceleration, velocity, displacement or strain) provided by a sensor network, $\mathbf{u}(k)$ is the input data of n_u input forces assumed to be measured by the sensor network, k denotes the time index at time t ($t = k\Delta t$) for n_d sampled data and Δt is the sampling period. The data $\mathbf{y}_\delta(k)$ depends on the sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ related to the type, number, location and measurement direction of sensors placed on the structure. Let $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the time histories of n response QoI predicted by the structural model for the specific values of the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ at all possible locations or DOF given the input time histories. These predictions depend also on a parameter set $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ that may include the excitation characteristics (e.g. amplitude and frequency content, random variables such as white noise variables defining the uncertain temporal and spatial variability of the excitation, number and location of actuators), and nuisance parameters associated with non-updatable parameters of the structural and/or prediction error model.

To account for modeling errors in the predictions, quantified by additive zero-mean Gaussian noise terms, the prediction from the model at the locations defined by the sensor configuration δ are expressed as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\delta}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \mathbf{L}(\delta) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) + \mathbf{L}(\delta) \mathbf{e}(k; \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{L}(\delta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n}$ is the selection matrix that selects the DOF from the response vector $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ that correspond to sensor configuration δ , $\mathbf{e} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e)$ is a zero-mean Gaussian measurement and model error term with a covariance equal to $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. Models for the prediction error covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e$ are introduced by following the approach used in [10, 35, 44]. The covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e$ is taken as

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = s^2 \mathbf{I} + \sigma_e^2 \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{1/2}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and the notation $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}$ denotes a diagonal matrix that contains in the i -th diagonal entry the square of the intensity of the i -th element of $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$. The first term in Eq. (2) accounts for the measurement error with error values to be independent of the response intensity, with the level s of the error to depend on the sensor accuracy and characteristics. The second term in Eq. (2) accounts for the model error. A reasonable choice of the model error variance at the i -th DOF is to have it proportional to the square of the intensity of the QoI at DOF i , given by $\mathbf{g}_i^2(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$, where σ_e denotes the level of model error in relation to the intensity of the QoI. Spatial correlation between prediction errors is neglected in the aforementioned formulation. Details about the correlation structure and its significance in structural dynamics can be found in [10].

Applying the Bayesian theorem, the posterior probability density function (PDF) of the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, given the measured data \mathbf{D} , takes the form

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{D}, \delta, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \tilde{c} \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2\pi})^{n_d} \sqrt{\det[\mathbf{L}(\delta) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \mathbf{L}^T(\delta)]}} \times \exp\left[-\frac{n_d n_y}{2} \mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{D}, \delta, \boldsymbol{\varphi})\right] \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{D}, \delta, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \frac{1}{n_d n_y} \sum_{k=1}^{n_d} [\mathbf{y}_{\delta}(k) - \mathbf{L}(\delta) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})]^T [\mathbf{L}(\delta) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \mathbf{L}^T(\delta)]^{-1} [\mathbf{y}_{\delta}(k) - \mathbf{L}(\delta) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})] \quad (4)$$

expresses the deviation between the measured and model predicted quantities. $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the prior distribution for $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \tilde{c} is a normalization constant guaranteeing that the posterior PDF $p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{D}, \delta, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ integrates to one. Eq. (3) quantifies the posterior uncertainty in the parameter values $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ based on the information contained in the measured data.

3. Bayesian Optimal Experimental Design Methodology

3.1. Information Content of Sensor Network for Parameter Estimation

The information content in the data is quantified through a utility function selected as the information gained by the experiment. The utility function is related to the relative entropy or the KL-div [38] between the prior and posterior PDF of the model parameters obtained for an experimental design δ . Using utility theory [50], the OED is accomplished by maximizing the expected information gain over all possible data generated from the prediction error model. It can be shown that asymptotically for large number of data and small prediction errors, the utility function that measures the expected information gain from the data for given $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$, can be simplified as follows [18, 19, 35, 42]:

$$\mathbf{U}(\delta, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = H_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) - \int_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} H_{\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{D}}(\delta; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) d\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (5)$$

where, using Eq. (3), $H_{\theta}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})$ is the information entropy of the prior PDF of the model parameters, $H_{\theta|D}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ is the average information entropy of the posterior PDF of the model parameters over all data, asymptotically approximated for large number of data by the expression [23, 44]

$$H_{\theta|D}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \frac{1}{2} n_{\theta} [\ln(2\pi) + 1] - \frac{1}{2} \ln \det [\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) + \mathbf{Q}_{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})] \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\theta} \times n_{\theta}}$ is the Fisher information matrix, a semi-positive definite matrix given by:

$$\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_d} \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\mathbf{L}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})]^T [\mathbf{L}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \mathbf{L}^T(\boldsymbol{\delta})]^{-1} \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^T [\mathbf{L}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})] \quad (7)$$

$\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = [\partial/\partial\theta_1, \dots, \partial/\partial\theta_{n_{\theta}}]$ is the gradient operator and $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ is the vector of response time histories at all possible sensor locations.

For truncated Gaussian prior distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = N_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$, where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}$ are respectively the mean vector and covariance of the corresponding Gaussian distribution $N(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi})$, and \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are vectors defining the lower and upper truncation bounds of the distribution, the information entropy of the prior distribution of the model parameters is given by

$$H_{\theta}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \frac{1}{2} n_{\theta} [\ln(2\pi) + 1] - \frac{1}{2} \ln \det [\mathbf{Q}_{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})] + h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}_{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})$ is the inverse of the covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}$ of the prior. For a Gaussian distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = N(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi})$, the last term $h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$. For independent components in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, each one following a truncated Gaussian distribution, denoted as $N_{\mathbf{T}}(\theta_i; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2, a_i, b_i)$ for the parameter θ_i , the function $h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ takes the form

$$h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\theta}} \left[\ln (\Phi(\beta_i) - \Phi(\alpha_i)) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\beta_i \phi(\beta_i) - \alpha_i \phi(\alpha_i)}{\Phi(\beta_i) - \Phi(\alpha_i)} \right] \quad (9)$$

where ϕ and Φ is the probability and the cumulative distribution function of a standard Gaussian variable, respectively, $\beta_i = (b_i - \mu_i)/\sigma_i$ and $\alpha_i = (a_i - \mu_i)/\sigma_i$, a_i and b_i are the lower and upper bounds of the truncated Gaussian distribution for the parameter θ_i , μ_i is the mean and σ_i is the standard deviation of the corresponding Gaussian distribution $N(\theta_i; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$.

Substituting the form of $h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ in Eq. (9) into Eq. (8) and then the resulting form of $H_{\theta}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})$ along with the form of $H_{\theta|D}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ in Eq. (6) into Eq. (5), the expected utility function finally takes the form

$$U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \Delta \bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = E_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta})] = \int_{\Theta} \Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) d\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = H_{\theta}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) - H_{\theta|D}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ is the change of the information entropy between the prior and the posterior distribution estimated at a parameter value $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ within the support of the prior distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, given by

$$\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{\det [\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) + \mathbf{Q}_{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})]}{\det \mathbf{Q}_{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})} + h_{\mathbf{T}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\pi}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \quad (11)$$

The utility function is based on the Fisher information matrix and it is an average of the information gain over all possible values of the model parameters over the support of the prior distribution, weighted by the values of the prior distribution. An estimate of the integral in Eq. (10) can be obtained using either Monte Carlo or Sparse Grids methods [51, 52] as follows:

$$U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = -E_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta})] \approx - \sum_{j=1}^N w_j \Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}$, $j = 1, \dots, N$ are sparse grid points or samples from the prior distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and w_j are the sparse grid or Monte Carlo weights.

3.2. Optimal Sensor Placement Conditional on $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$

The optimal values $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{opt}}$ of the design variables is obtained by maximizing the utility $U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ or, equivalently, minimizing the expected change in information entropy $\Delta\bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})$ taken with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ values over the support of the prior distribution, that is,

$$\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{opt}}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\delta}}{\operatorname{argmax}} U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\delta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \Delta\bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \quad (13)$$

The optimization problem involves discrete design variables $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ (e.g. DOF at nodes for placing displacement/acceleration sensors or Gauss integration points for placing strains sensors in a finite element mesh). Heuristic algorithms (e.g. [18]), including forward and backward sequential sensor placement (FSSP/BSSP) algorithms [10, 23], or genetic algorithms [1, 53, 54] can be employed to solve the optimization problem. The heuristic FSSP/BSSP algorithms bypass the problem of multiple local/global optima manifested in OSP, providing near optima solutions in a fraction of the computational effort required in stochastic optimization algorithms or exhaustive search methods [7]. The heuristic FFSP algorithm is used in this study. According to FSSP, the optimal (respectively worst) positions of n_y sensors are computed sequentially by placing one sensor at a time in the structure at a position that results in the highest (respectively smallest) increase in the utility value. Given that m sensors have been placed in the structure, the optimal position of the $(m + 1)$ sensor is obtained by an exhaustive search over all possible positions. As a result, the FSSP algorithm will give the optimal sensor layout for $m + 1$ sensors only if this sensor layout contains the sensor positions obtained in the optimal layout involving m sensors. Using the FSSP algorithm to obtain the sensors configuration for n_y sensors, one has as a by-product the sensor configurations involving m sensors with m ranging from 1 to n_y . It should be noted that the sensor configurations computed by the FSSP algorithm are approximate and cannot be guaranteed to be the optimal ones obtained by an exhaustive search algorithm. However, numerical applications have demonstrated that the FSSP algorithm provide near optimal solutions and in several cases the exact ones obtained by an exhaustive search algorithm [10, 23]. Also, FSSP is a computationally attractive alternative to the exact but computationally prohibitive exhaustive search method and also to the stochastic optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms [1, 54] that also provide near optimal solutions. Genetic algorithms can be used to improve the FSSP estimates, having better chances to converge to sensor layout corresponding to higher utility values than the ones provided by FSSP, with a much higher computational effort than FSSP.

3.3. Optimal Sensor Placement Considering Modeling and Input Uncertainties

The utility function in Eq. (10) depends on the values of the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$. The values of $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ are usually uncertain and this has to be accounted in the design of the optimal sensor configuration. The source of uncertainties vary from excitation uncertainties to structural model and prediction error model uncertainties. The excitation uncertainties are associated with the uncertain characteristics of environmental loads. Such loads are usually modelled by stochastic processes that correspond to a parameterized spectrum. For example, broad band laboratory loads applied from actuators or shake tables can be represented by white noise processes. Also, earthquake loads are often represented by the Kanai-Tajimi spectrum [45, 46] which belongs to a class of filtered white noise processes where the filter is represented by a second-order differential equation excited by white noise. More involved models [47–49] connected with the physics-based parameters such as earthquake source, source to site propagation properties, directional effects and local soil conditions also exist to characterize the

earthquake excitation uncertainties at a site by a stochastic process corresponding to a parameterized spectrum. The uncertain parameters $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ are associated with the Gaussian white noise sequence used to generate realization of the stochastic loads [48, 49] or the broadband laboratory loads, while Gaussian, truncated Gaussian, lognormal or other distributions are used to quantify the uncertainties in the parameters (intensity, frequency content) defining the spectrum of such stochastic loads. The OSP should be designed to cover all possible realizations of the stochastic process generated by all realizations of the load spectrum parameters.

The parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ is composed of two independent parameter sets, $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = (\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}})$, where the set $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}$ is associated with the Gaussian white noise sequence used for representing the stochastic nature of the excitation and the set $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}$ contains the parameter of the load spectrum, as well as the nuisance (non-updatable) parameters of the structural and prediction error models, such as the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (s, \sigma_e)$ in Eq. (2). Using the fact that the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ is an uncertain vector modelled by a prior probability distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}})$, the information contained in the sensor measurements is defined to be the expected information gain, quantified by the expected utility function

$$U(\boldsymbol{\delta}) = \int_{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) d\boldsymbol{\varphi} = - \int_{\boldsymbol{\Phi}} \int_{\Theta} \Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) d\boldsymbol{\varphi} d\boldsymbol{\theta} \equiv -\Delta \bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \quad (14)$$

over all possible values of the parameter set $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$. The optimal sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{opt}}$ is selected to optimize the expected utility function, i.e.

$$\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{opt}} = \underset{\boldsymbol{\delta}}{\operatorname{argmax}} U(\boldsymbol{\delta}) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\delta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \Delta \bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \quad (15)$$

over all possible sensor configurations $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, where $\Delta \bar{H}(\boldsymbol{\delta})$ is the expected change in the information entropy between the prior and posterior distribution.

An estimate of the multidimensional integral in Eq. (14) can be obtained using Monte Carlo sampling for the white noise sequence parameters, while the parameters of the spectrum can be treated exactly the same as the model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ so that sparse grid or Monte Carlo estimates can be used to estimate the integral in the form

$$U(\boldsymbol{\delta}) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)}) \quad (16)$$

where

$$U(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}) = -E_{\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}} [\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \{\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}\}, \boldsymbol{\theta})] \approx - \sum_{j=1}^N w_j \Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \{\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}^{(j)}\}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) \quad (17)$$

For each white noise sequence, Eq. (17) averages over all possible values of the model parameters in the support of the prior distributions of the updatable and non-updatable parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}$, respectively, using the sampled values of the updatable model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}$ and the nuisance model parameters $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}^{(j)}$, $j = 1, \dots, N$. Eq. (16) averages the utility function over different realizations of the white noise sequence and represents robustness in the time history details of the stochastic excitation.

The computationally most efficient algorithm to perform the OSP with FSSP is to avoid re-computing the sensitivities of the time history responses in Eq. (7) with respect to the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ for sensor configurations that contain common locations. These sensitivities have to be computed once and then stored for all possible sensor locations. This computation has to be repeated for each sample $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}$ and

$\boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(j)}$ of the updatable and non-updatable (nuisance) model parameter drawn from the prior distribution and for each realization $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)}$ of the stochastic input variables. An algorithm for computing the utility function $U(\boldsymbol{\delta})$ given a sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is given in Algorithm 1. The algorithm consists of two steps. In the first step, the sensitivities of the response at all possible sensor locations to updatable parameter values in the set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are computed and stored for all samples $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(j)}$ as well excitation time history samples $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)}$. In the second step, the computation of the utility is evaluated for each sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ by using the stored sensitivities.

Algorithm 1: Estimation of the expected information gain robust to model and input uncertainties

Step 1: Compute and store response sensitivities at all possible sensor locations

- 1.1 for $i = 1 : M$
generate samples $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)}$ from prior PDF $\pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}})$ of the white-noise variables $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}$
 - 1.2 for $j = 1 : N$
generate samples $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}^{(j)}$ from prior PDF $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and $\pi(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}})$ of the updatable and non-updatable parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}$, respectively
 - 1.3 Compute response vector $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and response sensitivities $\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\theta} \times n}$ using the equations of motion and equations of the sensitivity of responses to parameter uncertainty, where $\boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)} = (\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)})$; Compute also the intensities of the responses included in the response vector $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})$
 - 1.4 Store the intensities of the responses $\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for each i and j and also store the response sensitivities $\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\theta} \times n}$ for each i, j and k
end j
end i
-

Step 2: For each sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ required in the optimization algorithm compute the expected information gain $U(\boldsymbol{\delta})$ as follows:

- 2.1 Form the selection matrix $L(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n}$ that corresponds to sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$
 - 2.2 For $i = 1 : M$
Load from the stored values $\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [\mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\theta} \times n}$, $j = 1, \dots, N$, $i = 1, \dots, M$, for all possible sensor locations, the response sensitivities $\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} [L(\boldsymbol{\delta}) \mathbf{g}(k; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\theta} \times n_y}$ corresponding to the sensor configuration $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, required in the FIM in Eq. (7);
Compute $\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)})$ from Eq. (7) and $\Delta H(\boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}^{(ij)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})$ from Eq. (11);
Compute the expected information gain $U(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)})$ from Eq. (17), conditional on the input realization i
end i
 - 2.3 Compute $U(\boldsymbol{\delta})$ from Eq. (16) from the individual information gain values $U(\boldsymbol{\delta}; \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{wn}}^{(i)})$ for each input realization i
-

3.4. Computational Cost and Storage Requirements

The sensitivity computations can substantially increase the computational burden of the methodology as well as the storage requirements, especially when the number n of possible sensor locations, number N of samples drawn from the prior distribution and the number M of input realizations are large. The computational burden depends on the number of runs required to compute the response sensitivities. For the case that the response sensitivities can be obtained analytically by direct differentiation methods, the number of simulation runs for solving the equations for the sensitivities of the response to each parameter are as many as the number of model parameters n_θ . For n number of possible sensor locations, N number of samples in Eq. (17), M input realizations in Eq. (16), n_θ number of updatable model parameters, and n_d points in a time history, the total number of simulation is thus $n_\theta NM$, while the storage requirements are of the order of $8n_\theta n n_d NM 10^{-9}$ GB. Once the response sensitivities have been stored, the optimization of the utility function is performed with the utility built from the stored response sensitivities.

To get an idea of the computational cost and the storage requirements, for the small case of $n_\theta = 10$, $n = 100$, $N = 100$, $M = 100$ and $n_d = 100$ the system simulation runs is of the order of 10^5 and the storage requirement is 8GB, while for a moderate case of $n_\theta = 10$, $n = 1000$, $N = 1000$, $M = 1000$ and $n_d = 1000$ the simulation runs is of the order of 10^7 and the storage requirements is 8×10^4 GB. It is obvious that the computational cost and especially the storage requirements can become excessive even for moderate cases encountered in structural dynamics. Parallel computing can help to scale the computational effort by the number of available cores available.

4. Application and Numerical Results

Without loss of generality, the application in this work is confined to MDOF nonlinear spring-mass chain models shown in Fig. 1. The restoring force is considered to be hysteretic, modelled by Bouc-Wen model [55, 56]. The equations of motion are briefly summarized in Appendix A.1 and extended in Appendix A.2 for ground excitations modelled by filtered white noise input. Direct differentiation techniques are used to develop the equations for the response sensitivities with respect to the model parameters for the Bouc-Wen restoring force nonlinearity, required in the OSP formulation (see Eq. (7)).

Figure 1: Multi DOF nonlinear spring-mass chain model.

4.1. 6-DOF nonlinear spring-mass system

A 6 DOF nonlinear spring-mass chain model of the structure is first considered (Fig. 1). The structure could be a 6-story building represented by a shear model with each link modeling the interstory stiffness and each mass modelling the floor mass. Rayleigh damping $\mathbf{C} = \alpha_R \mathbf{M} + \beta_R \mathbf{K}$ is assumed with $\alpha_R = 0.23$ and $\beta_R = 0.001$, where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} are the mass and stiffness matrices of the linear model of the system corresponding to identical nominal values $k_i = k_0 = 200$ Nt/m and identical mass values selected to give lowest modal frequency equal to 1.09 Hz. The parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is introduced for the 1st and the 2nd links of the chain model. The parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ includes the stiffness k and the Bouc-Wen model parameters A, β, α, n of the 1st and 2nd links. γ is assigned to be $1 - \beta$. The model parameters of two links are assumed to be independent from each other. Thus the number of model parameters to be inferred is 10. It is assumed that the other springs are linear. A Gaussian prior PDF is assumed for each model parameter in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ with mean μ and standard deviation σ given in Table 1. The bounds of Bouc-Wen model parameters are selected to meet the following conditions: $A > 0, n > 1, \beta > 0, \alpha \in (0, 1)$.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of Gaussian distribution, $\theta_i \sim N(\mu, \sigma)$, quantifying the prior information of the model parameters θ_i .

Parameter	(μ, σ)
$k_1/k_0, k_2/k_0$	(1, 0.2)
A_1, A_2	(1, 0.2)
β_1, β_2	(0.7, 0.2)
n_1, n_2	(2, 0.2)
α_1, α_2	(0.5, 0.1)

The objective of the application is to find an optimal acceleration sensor placement layout that maximizes the information for estimating the model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The time histories of the response used for the OSP are contained in the interval $[t_1, t_1 + T]$ where the variable t_1 is chosen to be $t_1 = 1$ sec in order to reduce the transient effects and T is chosen to be $T = 10$ sec in order to have a reasonable signal duration to be a multiple of the largest modal period of 0.92 sec computed for the linear part of the model for the nominal values of the model parameters.

The structure is subjected to a base acceleration modelled by a zero-mean Gaussian white noise process with variance c^2 , defined at discrete times with time step $dt = 0.01$ sec. The amplitude c is selected to be $c = 100$ in order to activate model nonlinearities. The nonlinear restoring force of the 1st and 2nd links to the white noise input, normalized by structure's inertia corresponding to the input intensity, is presented in Fig. 2 for the nominal values of the model parameters. Fig. 3 shows the intensities (root-mean-square of the responses) of the acceleration responses at the six DOF, normalized by the base acceleration intensity.

Figure 2: Normalized hysteretic force versus story drift, normalized by the maximum displacement, for the first and second link computed for the nominal (mean) values of model parameters ($k_i = 1, A_i = 1, \beta_i = 0.7, \gamma_i = 0.3, n = 2, \alpha_i = 0.5, i = 1, 2$).

Figure 3: Normalized intensities of absolute accelerations for mean values of the model parameters versus DOF.

4.1.1. Effect of model and measurement error parameters

The effects of the model and measurement error parameters on OSP is explored by considering the different measurement and model error cases given in Table 2. For error cases 1 and 5, the standard deviations for the error covariance matrices are selected so that the model error corresponds to 1% (small model error) and 10% (large model error) of the intensity of measured QoI, while the measurement error is fixed to 0.4% (small measurement error) of the average intensity of the measured QoI given in Fig. 3. For cases 1 to 4, the model error is fixed to 1% (small) of the intensity of measured QoI, while the measurement error corresponds to 0.4% (small), 1% (moderate), 4% (large) and 40% (very large) of the average intensity of measured QoI given in Fig. 3.

Table 2: Different cases of model and measurement error parameters. ϵ_{rms} is the intensity (root mean square) of the floor absolute accelerations.

Case	model error	measurement error	σ_e	s	s/ϵ_{rms}
1	small	very small	0.01	0.1	$\sim 0.4\%$
2	small	small	0.01	0.3	$\sim 1\%$
3	small	moderate	0.01	1	$\sim 4\%$
4	small	large	0.01	10	$\sim 40\%$
5	large	small	0.1	0.1	$\sim 0.4\%$

To consider the uncertainty in the unknown temporal variability of the input, the OSP design is based on 100 realizations of the white noise input. The expectation over the uncertain input parameter space is calculated using the expected information gain (utility) values in Eq. (14) as a function of the number of sensors placed at their optimal locations. Results are presented in Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(b) shows the utility values normalized by the maximum utility value for the sensor configuration containing six sensors. Results obtained from different error cases are compared in these figures.

Figure 4: (a) Maximum utility values and (b) normalized maximum and minimum utilities values as a function of the number of sensors.

As observed from the expected utility values, there is a significant information gain when sensors are placed to the system to estimate the model parameters. Depending on the model and measurement error case, the first sensor optimally located on the structure provides 71-87% of the information that one would get by placing all six acceleration sensors in all six DOF. Each additional sensor provides some extra information for estimating the model parameters, until the maximum information is reached for 6 sensors. From Fig. 4(a) results, as measurement error increases from case 1 to case 4, the information gain decreases, which is consistent with intuition that higher measurement error corresponds to higher noise to signal ratio in the measurements and thus the information recovered is less. In the presence of noisy signals, one requires more sensors to gain the same information for parameter estimation. A similar trend can be observed for the model error comparison between case 1 and case 5. Higher model error requires more sensors to gain the same information as one gains with smaller model error.

The optimal and the worst sensor locations are computed using the heuristic FSSP algorithm and shown in Fig. 5 as a function of the number of sensors. According to the approximate FSSP algorithm, the optimal sensor layout for $m + 1$ sensors is the optimal sensor layout estimated for m sensors with the addition of the best location for the $(m + 1)$ -th sensor. Thus, the information in Fig. 5(a) should be interpreted as follows. For example, for the Case 4 the optimal configuration for 3 sensors is the configuration with the sensors placed at DOF 1, 6 and 2, while the optimal sensor configuration for 4 sensors is the configuration with the sensors placed at DOF 1, 6, 2 and 3. Similarly, from the results in Fig. 5(b) for the Case 4, the worst sensor configuration for 3 sensors involves the sensors placed at DOF 5, 4 and 3, while the worst sensor configuration for 4 sensors is the configuration with sensors placed at DOF 5, 4, 3 and 6. The best locations for the most informative sensor configurations and the worst locations for the least informative sensor configurations for all sensors are found to slightly depend on the model and measurement error cases. According to the optimal sensor location result, the 1st sensor should be placed in the 1st DOF, independently of the model and measurement error case considered, to reliably estimate the model parameters associated with the 1st and 2nd links. This optimal location turns out to be the location between the two links that involve the unknown parameters to be inferred from the measurements. The best location of the second sensors turns out to be the 2nd DOF for most error cases and DOF 6 for the case of large measurement error. For almost all cases, the worst location of one sensor is 5th or 6th DOF, which correspond to DOF that are further away from the parameterized first two links.

In almost most measurement/model error cases, the best sensor configuration for two sensors contains DOF 1 and 2, while the worst sensor configuration for two sensors contains DOF 6 and 5. It should be noted that for a sensor configuration that involves 4 sensors, the best sensor locations corresponding to the largest utility value and the worst sensor locations corresponding to the smallest utility value include DOF 3 and 4. This is not surprising and should be expected due to the limited number of DOF since, for example, the best sensor configuration with four sensors contains DOF 1-4 and avoids the selection of the remaining DOF 6 and 5 that, from the utility values for one and two sensors in Figure 5, are found to provide the least information.

Figure 5: The best and worst sensor locations as a function of the number of sensors.

4.1.2. Computational Issues

For the 6 DOF system, the size of the input file (the actual storage requirements) for 100 white noise input realizations is $8n_{\theta}nn_dNM10^{-9} = 8 \times 10 \times 6 \times 1001 \times 400 \times 100 \times 10^{-9} = 19$ GB. To create the input file for 100 white noise input cases, $n_{\theta}NM = 10 \times 400 \times 100 = 4 \times 10^5$ runs of the response sensitivity equations is required which amounts to 4.5 hours of computation time performed in a 32-core computer to handle the problem in parallel workers. Finally, the optimization over the sensor configuration, performed using the stored values for the response sensitivities, takes around 30 min with FSSP algorithm, which amounts to 10% of the time required to compute and store the response sensitivities. These estimates should be compared to the ones corresponding to a single input time history ($M = 1$) used when neglecting input uncertainties. The storage requirements is 0.19 GB and the computational time for running the sensitivity equations is less than 3 min and can be considered to be negligible.

4.1.3. Effect of input intensity

To explore the effect of the input intensity, the OSP problem is solved with different values c of the white noise excitation intensity, ranging from 0.1 to 500, and for the measurement and model error case 3 (small model error and moderate measurement error) presented in Table 2. In this analysis, only 1 white noise input realization is considered. Results for the maximum information gain are presented in Fig. 6 for three different sensor configurations corresponding to 1, 3 and 6 number of sensors. As expected, the information gain is increasing with the input amplitude since as the values of the input intensity increase, the level of nonlinearity in the system links are progressively activated into higher levels and thus more information can be extracted from the data to reliably estimate parameters related to the nonlinearity. The higher the value of the input intensity, the smaller the increase in the information gain. As the value of the intensity increases, a sharper increase of the information gain is observed for smaller values of the input intensity c since the system moves progressively from a linear or weakly nonlinear state to a strongly nonlinear state. Once the nonlinearities are strongly activated, further increase of the intensity causes the system nonlinearities to increase further but the extra information contained in the data is relatively small compared to the information gain obtained for smaller intensities that strongly activate the nonlinearities. Specifically, it can be noted that the increase of the intensity from 200 to 500 results in an extra information gain of 3 for one optimally placed sensor, which is only a small fraction of approximately 10% of the information gain of 27 obtained from an increase of c from 0.1 to 200.

Figure 6: Maximum utility values versus input intensity for white noise input obtained with 1, 3 and 6 sensors.

4.1.4. Effect of prior uncertainty

To investigate the effect of prior uncertainty, the problem is solved with truncated Gaussian prior distributions. The truncated Gaussian distribution $N_T(\theta; \mu, \sigma, a, b)$ is used in order to be able to increase the uncertainty in the prior of the updated parameters, avoiding the violation of hard constraints in the allowable values of the model parameters. The parameters μ , σ and the bounds a and b of the truncated prior distribution are given in Table 3. Results are obtained for only a single input white noise realization and for model and measurement error case 3. Results are compared in Fig. 7 for different values of the standard deviation σ : 0.2, 0.5, 1 and 10. The increase of the uncertainty of prior distribution leads to an increase in the utility values. This is consistent with the fact that the apparent information gain that a given set of data provides is larger for larger uncertainty in the prior. This is due to the fact that large prior uncertainty corresponds to smaller values of $\det \mathbf{Q}_\pi$ in Eq. (11), while for a fixed Fisher information matrix \mathbf{Q} determined from the data, the contribution of \mathbf{Q}_π in $\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{Q}_\pi$ is negligible. As a result, the increase in the uncertainty in the prior results in a decrease in the denominator in Eq. (11) which corresponds to an increase in the utility value. From the normalized utility values in Fig. 7(b), it can be concluded that the normalized information gain, seen as a fraction of the maximum information gain that can be achieved for 6 sensors, is almost independent of the large differences in the prior uncertainty.

Table 3: Mean, standard deviation and bounds of truncated Gaussian distribution, $\theta_i \sim N_T(\mu, \sigma, a, b)$, quantifying the prior information of the model parameters θ_i .

Parameter	(μ, σ, a, b)
k_1, k_2	$(1, \sigma, 0.4, 1.6)$
A_1, A_2	$(1, \sigma, 0.1, 10)$
β_1, β_2	$(0.7, \sigma, 0.1, 2)$
n_1, n_2	$(2, \sigma, 1.1, 5)$
α_1, α_2	$(0.5, \sigma, 0.1, 0.9)$

Figure 7: Maximum and minimum (a) utility values and (b) normalized utility values using truncated Gaussian priors.

4.2. 20-DOF nonlinear spring-mass system

As a second numerical example, a 20 DOF nonlinear spring-mass chain model of the structure shown in Fig. 1 is considered. The modal frequencies of the linear system, with nominal stiffness

values $k_i = k_0 = 600$ Nt/m and equal masses, are given in Table 4. The nonlinearity in the system is defined in the form of a Bouc-Wen hysteresis model for the links 1 to 5. It is assumed that the stiffness of the other links are linear. Rayleigh damping $\mathbf{C} = \alpha_R \mathbf{M} + \beta_R \mathbf{K}$ is assumed with $\alpha_R = 0.48$ and $\beta_R = 0.004$, where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} are the mass and stiffness matrices of the linear model of the system. The parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ includes the stiffness k and the Bouc-Wen model parameters A, β, n and α for each link from 1-5 floors. γ is assigned to be $1 - \beta$. The model parameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ for links 1 to 4 are considered fully correlated. The model parameters of link 5 are treated as independent of the model parameters of link 1 to 4. Thus, the number of modal parameters is 10. A Gaussian prior PDF is assumed for each model parameter with mean μ and standard deviation σ given in Table 5. The Case 3 (Table 2) of small model and moderate measurement error is considered. For each white noise input realization, the Monte Carlo method with 400 samples is used to calculate the integration in the utility calculation over the support of the prior values of model parameters $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{nu}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

Table 4: Modal frequencies of the linear system.

Mode	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20
Freq.(Hz)	1.02	3.07	5.09	7.09	9.04	10.94	12.78	14.54	16.21	17.79	26.66

Table 5: Mean and standard deviation of Gaussian distribution, $\theta_i \sim N(\mu, \sigma)$, quantifying the prior information of the model parameters.

Parameter	(μ, σ)
$k_{1,2,3,4}/k_0, k_5/k_0$	(1, 0.2)
$A_{1,2,3,4}, A_5$	(1, 0.2)
$\beta_{1,2,3,4}, \beta_5$	(0.7, 0.2)
$n_{1,2,3,4}, n_5$	(2, 0.2)
$\alpha_{1,2,3,4}, \alpha_5$	(0.5, 0.1)

4.2.1. Uncertainties in white-noise input characteristics

The structure is subjected to a broadband base acceleration modelled by a discrete zero-mean Gaussian white noise process with variance c^2 ($c = 800$) selected so that the nonlinearities are activated. The time samples are given every $dt = 0.01$ sec. The normalized hysteresis force versus the normalized story drift calculated with the mean values of estimated parameters for the lowest five stories is given in Fig. 8 for a specific realization of the white noise excitation and for c values ranging from 400 to 1000. For the OSP, the chosen time interval is $[t_1, t_1 + T]$ where $t_1 = 1$ sec is selected to reduce the effect of the transient part of the response, and $T = 2, T = 5$ and $T = 10$ sec are selected to be able to study the effect of time duration on the information gain. To consider the effect of the input uncertainty, the expectation over 100 different white noise input realizations is calculated using Eq. (14).

Figure 8: Normalized hysteretic force versus normalized story drift with mean values of updated parameters for different excitation intensities c .

The maximum and minimum utility values, computed using the heuristic FSSP algorithm, as well as the normalized utility values are presented in Fig. 9. The best and worst sensor locations are presented in Fig. 10. From the utility results, it can be seen that the information gain is affected by the signal duration. The higher the signal duration, the more the information provided from the data. However, from the normalized utility values in Fig. 9(b), it can be seen that the maximum information gain from an optimal sensor configuration involving a fixed number of sensors, measured as a fraction of the maximum information that can be gained by placing as many as 20 acceleration sensors, is almost independent of the duration of the excitation. From Fig. 10, the same can be concluded for the optimal and the worst sensor locations since these locations are almost independent of the signal duration. As a result, the OSP for a signal duration remains optimal for any other signal duration, in terms of normalized information gain and optimal sensor locations.

For the three cases of signal duration, there is a significant gain of approximately 75% of the maximum information when the first sensors is placed to its optimal location. According to the optimal sensor location result, the first 3 sensor locations are not affected from the signal duration and they should be placed to 4th, 5th and 3rd DOF to reliably estimate the model parameters of the first 5 links. The best locations for more than 3 sensors are slightly different for the three different signal durations. However, these different sensor configurations are nearly optimal since they provide utility values that are close to the maximum utility values. The worst locations of the first sensor is the 17th DOF providing 57% to 66% of the maximum information that can be achieved by placing acceleration sensors at all 20 DOF.

Figure 9: Maximum and minimum (a) Utility values, and (b) normalized utility values robust to input characteristics for different signal duration $T = 2, 5$ and 10 sec.

Figure 10: (a) Best and (b) worst sensor locations robust to input characteristics for different signal duration $T = 2, 5$ and 10 sec.

The optimal location of sensors as a function of the number of sensors are reported in Fig. 11 for each one of the 100 different realizations of the stochastic excitation. For comparison purposes, the optimal sensor locations corresponding to the expected utility values that take into account the input uncertainties are also shown in this figure. The optimal sensor locations show a slight dependence on the details of the input realizations of the stochastic excitation. The robust optimal location of the first sensor is DOF 4. This OSP at DOF 4 for the first sensor is preferred for all 100 input realizations. The robust optimal location of the second sensor is DOF 5. The DOF 5 is preferred as optimal location of the second sensor for 99 input realization cases. The second preferred location of the second sensor is DOF 3 for 1 input realization. For the third sensor, the robust position is DOF 3, while the optimal position for each input realization is shared among DOF 3 (65% of the input realizations), DOF 20 (34% of the input realizations), and DOF 5 (1% of the input realizations).

Figure 11: Optimal sensor locations as a function of the number of sensors for 100 different input realizations. For a given number of sensors, more than one sensors locations can be predicted out of the 100 input realizations. The size of the blue square marker is selected to be proportional to the number of occurrence of the best sensor locations counted among the 100 input realizations. Also, the robust optimal sensor locations are shown with yellow triangle.

For the 20 DOF system, the storage requirements for 100 white noise input realizations are $8n_{\theta}nn_dNM10^{-9} = 8 \times 10 \times 20 \times 1000 \times 400 \times 100 \times 10^{-9} = 64$ GB. To create the input file for 100 white noise input realizations, $n_{\theta} \times N \times M = 10 \times 400 \times 100 = 4 \times 10^5$ runs of the sensitivity equations is required which amounts to 26 hours of computation time required in a 32-core computer to handle the problem in parallel workers. Finally, the optimization over the sensor configuration, performed using the stored values for each sensor involved in a sensor configuration to compute the utility, takes around 3 hours with FSSP, which amounts to almost 10% of the time required to compute and store the response sensitivities. These estimates should be compared to the ones corresponding to a single input time history ($M = 1$) used when ignoring input uncertainties. In this case the storage requirements reduce to 0.64 Gb, while the computational effort required in the first step of deriving the response sensitivities is substantially reduced to less than 15 min.

4.2.2. Uncertainties in white noise input intensity

To consider the uncertainty in white noise intensity, the parameter c is assumed to follow a truncated Gaussian distribution $N(c|\mu_c, \sigma_c, 0, \infty)$ with mean parameter $\mu_c = 800$ and standard deviation parameter $\sigma_c = 0.3\mu_c = 240$. For the OSP, a time interval $[t_1, t_1 + T]$ is chosen with $t_1 = 1$ and $T = 10$ sec.

Results for the maximum utility values as a function of the number of acceleration sensors placed at the optimal position, as well as the optimal and worst sensor locations are compared in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 for the deterministic $c = 800$ value and for the uncertain c case. The results for both the deterministic and the uncertain c cases are estimated for only a single realization of the white noise input. According to the utility results, the uncertain c case gives information gain values that are higher than the ones for the deterministic case. This is due to the fact that in the uncertain case, the values of c increase significantly, activating large levels of nonlinearities, and thus there is more information in the data to estimate the parameters related to the nonlinear restoring force. From the results in Fig. 12, the maximum normalized information gain for both deterministic $c = 800$ case and the uncertain c case is almost the same for all optimal sensor configurations involving various number of sensors. In particular, approximately 80% of the maximum information can be obtained by using 1 sensor, with each additional sensor providing some extra information for estimating the model parameters of the lowest 5 nonlinear stories.

Results in Fig. 13 suggest that the optimal sensor configuration involving one, two or four sensors is not affected by the uncertainty in c . The optimal location of 3 sensors differs, with the third sensor placed optimally at the 20-th DOF for the uncertain c case as opposed to the 3-rd DOF placed for the deterministic c case. However, both optimal sensor configurations predicted by the deterministic and uncertain c cases for 3 sensors provide normalized information gains that are higher than 99% of the maximum information gain that can be achieved for 3 sensors for the uncertain and deterministic c cases, respectively. Thus, in this particular example, the OSP computed for 3 sensors for the deterministic c case is near optimal configuration for the uncertain c case. The optimal and worst sensor configurations for 1 to 20 sensors give almost the same pattern, as seen in Fig. 13, for both the deterministic and uncertain c cases.

Figure 12: Comparison of (a) Utility values, and (b) normalized utility values for the deterministic ($c = 800$) and uncertain input intensity c .

Figure 13: Comparison of (a) best and (b) worst sensor locations for the deterministic ($c = 800$) and uncertain input intensity c .

4.2.3. Uncertainties in filtered input characteristics

The structure is next subjected to a base excitation modelled by the output of the Kanai-Tajimi (KT) model used to simulated earthquake excitations. In [57] the use of $\zeta = 0.64$ and $\omega_g = 15.56$ (rad/sec) is recommended for firm soil conditions in a frequency range from 2.1 (rad/sec) to 21 (rad/sec). In this example, ζ_g is assumed to be constant equal to 0.64, and ω_g is assumed to be uncertain following a Gaussian distribution with mean 15 (rad/sec) and standard deviation 1.5 (rad/sec). The intensity of the filtered input is kept equal to $c_f = 400$ for all values of ω_f , in order to activate nonlinearities in the first five links. In Fig. 14, comparison of the white noise and the filtered input normalized by the input intensity, and the normalized hysteretic force and story drifts (for the first 5 stories) calculated by using the mean values of updated and uncertain model parameter is seen. Case 3 of the small model and moderate measurement error reported in Table 2 is considered.

Figure 14: (a) Comparison of the normalized input (blue-solid) and filtered input (red-dashed) in time and frequency domain, (b) normalized hysteretic restoring force versus normalized story drift for the first 5 stories estimated using the mean values of model parameters.

The portion of the response that is included in the utility estimation corresponds to the time interval $[t_1, t_1 + T]$, where t_1 is selected so that the transient part of the response decays sufficiently, while the duration T is chosen to be a multiple of the lower modal period of the linear system so that and the response within the interval T achieves stationarity. The following choices are made $t_1 = 1$ sec and $T = 10$ sec in order to keep the computational effort to manageable levels.

The OSP is computed to take into account the uncertainties of the filter parameter ω_g and the time history details of the earthquake excitation. To consider the earthquake acceleration uncertainty, 100 different filtered white noise input realizations are generated and the utility is averaged over all input representations. The Monte Carlo method is used to estimate the integral involved in the utility over

the possible values of parameters to be inferred and the uncertain input parameter with 400 samples.

The robust OSP results obtained using the expected utility value over all realizations are compared with the results obtained by maximizing the utility value for each one of the 100 realizations of the stochastic excitation. For this, the upper and lower bounds in the maximum and minimum utility values computed by using 100 realizations are shown in Fig. 15(a). The maximum and minimum utility values corresponding to the robust OSP obtained by considering the expected utility averaged over the 100 input realization is also presented in Fig. 15(a). The upper and lower bounds for the normalized information gain values are shown in Fig. 15(b).

Figure 15: Upper bounds (UB) and lower bounds (LB) of maximum and minimum information gain for 100 different input realizations, as well as maximum and minimum of the expected information entropy robust to input uncertainties. (a) Expected utility values, and (b) normalized expected utility values.

It can be seen that the maximum and minimum utility values are affected from the details of the stochastic excitation. Specifically, the maximum and the minimum utility values depend on the input realization and may vary by approximately 20 to 30% depending on the number of sensors in a configuration. Similar variation is evident for the minimum utility values. However, the normalized utility values, normalized with respect to the maximum information gain that can be achieved by as many as 20 acceleration sensors, demonstrate a smaller variability, lower than 7%. In addition, the expected utility values and the normalized expected utility values that take into account the input uncertainties are contained within the aforementioned bounds. The results in Fig. 15(a) suggest that the uncertainty in the details of the input excitation does not considerably affect the information gain as a function of the number of optimally placed sensors in relation to the maximum information gain that can be achieved by populating the structure with the maximum of 20 sensors. 75% of the maximum information can be obtained by using 1 sensor and after that each additional sensors provides some extra information for estimating the model parameters of the lower 5 links in the chain.

The optimal and worst location of sensors as a function of the number of sensors are reported in Fig. 16 for each one of the 100 different realizations of the stochastic excitation. The optimal and worst sensor locations corresponding to the expected utility values that take into account the input uncertainties are also shown in this figure. The optimal and worst sensor locations in Fig. 16 show a slight dependence on the details of the input realizations of the stochastic excitation. The robust optimal location of the first sensor is DOF 4, while the OSP at DOF 4 for the first sensor is preferred 88% of 100 input realizations, with the second preferred location of the first sensor to be DOF 3. Similar

results are obtained for the second sensor. The robust optimal sensor location of the second sensor is DOF 1. The preferred locations of the second sensor are DOF 1 for 88 input realizations and DOF 20 for the remaining 12 input realizations. For the third sensors, the robust position is found to be DOF 20, while the optimal position for each input realization is shared among DOF 20 (71% of the input realizations), DOF 5 (17% of the input realizations) and DOF 1 (12% of the input realizations). Finally, the robust OSP for 1 to 4 sensors are DOF 4, 1, 20 and 5, while the OSP predicted by the 100 input realizations is 4 (88% occurrence), 1 (88% occurrence), 20 (71% occurrence) and 5 (60% occurrence). Similar to the best sensors location results, worst locations are also found to be less sensitive to the changes in the white noise input characteristics.

Figure 16: (a) Optimal and (b) worst sensor locations as a function of the number of sensors for 100 different stochastic input realizations. For a given number of sensors, more than one sensors locations can be predicted out of the 100 input realizations. The size of the blue square marker is selected to be proportional to the number of occurrence of each best/worst sensor locations counted among the 100 input realizations. Also, the robust (a) optimal and (b) worst sensor locations are shown with yellow triangle.

It should be noted that although the DOF predicted by a fraction of the 100 input realization are not contained in the robust estimate, the different OSP estimates proposed by each one of the 100 input realizations do correspond to near optimal solutions when the robust utility is computed. To demonstrate this, the optimal sensor configuration computed for each one of the 100 input realizations is used to compute the expected information gain taking into account the input uncertainty. The ratio of the resulting information gain values to the maximum expected information gain values is computed as a function of the number of sensors for all 100 input realizations. The lower and upper bounds of this ratio as a function of the number of sensors are plotted in Fig. 17. The values of the ratio are extremely close to one, ranging from 0.985 to 1.0, signifying that the information loss obtained by designing the optimal sensor configuration based on a single input realization, any single one out of the 100 input realizations, is not higher than 1 to 1.5%. This result promotes the idea of using a single realization of a stochastic excitation to design the optimal sensor configuration and find a near optimal solution, thus avoiding the very high computational cost and storage requirements associated with maximizing the expected information gain over all possible values of the input realizations.

Figure 17: Lower and upper bounds as a function of the number of sensors of the ratio of the expected information gain values computed from the OSP corresponding to each one of the 100 input realization and the maximum expected (robust) information gain values.

To investigate the effect of the number of parameters to be inferred and the spread of parameters along the structure, the final case considered is the OSP for estimating the parameters of the lower five links, assuming that the values of the five parameters k , A , β , n and α of each link are independent, totalling to as many as 25 parameters. A truncated Gaussian prior PDF is assumed for each model parameter θ with mean μ and standard deviation σ given in Table 5. The ground acceleration input is considered to follow the Kanai-Tajimi model with $\omega_g = 15$ Hz and $\zeta_g = 0.64$. The intensity of the filtered input is kept equal to be $c_f = 400$ in order to activate nonlinearities in the lower five links. Case 3 of the model and measurement error reported in Table 2 is considered.

Results for the maximum and minimum utility values as a function of acceleration sensors placed at their optimal locations are presented in Fig. 18 for 5 different realizations of the stochastic ground excitation. The corresponding optimal and worst sensors locations are given in Fig. 19. It is observed that there is no significant variability in the maximum information gain values among the 5 different input realizations, while the variability in the normalized utility values is extremely small. Also, the optimal sensor locations predicted by the five different input realizations coincide for sensor configuration involving 1 and up to 11 sensors. Similar results are obtained for the worst sensor configurations estimated from the 5 different input realizations. These results confirm that it suffices to use a single input realization from a stochastic process to find a near optimum sensor configuration, thus avoiding the computationally very expensive process and reducing the storage requirements that may arise from averaging the utility function over all possible input realizations. Nevertheless, the last argument should be used with care since it is found to hold for the specific examples considered in this work and may not be generalizable to other systems and stochastic representations of loads. However, given the necessary computing facilities, the proposed technique can properly find the robust OSP that accounts for the uncertainties arising from variabilities in the input time histories.

Figure 18: Maximum and minimum (a) Utility values, and (b) normalized utility values for different realizations of the excitation.

Figure 19: (a) Best and (b) worst sensor locations for different realizations of the excitation.

5. Conclusion

A Bayesian OSP framework is presented for parameter estimation of linear and nonlinear models in structural dynamics using input-output response time history measurements. The effects of modeling and input uncertainties are comprehensively investigated in this study. Past studies considered in the OSP that the excitation is available. However, although the time histories of the inputs can be measured during the inference process with appropriately installed sensors, such inputs are not available during OSP phase. For this, the temporal variability of the inputs is described in this work using stochastic process models. Examples include the use of white noise models to represent broadband excitations generated by actuators and shake tables in laboratory experiments, as well as the use of stochastic models such as the Kanai-Tajimi model or available seismological models for quantifying the earthquake excitation process at the base of a monitored structure. This study recognises the

uncertainties in the excitation time histories and proposes an optimal design that is robust to such uncertainties.

The design variables include the locations of the sensors. Information and utility theory are used to define the objective function to be maximized, measuring the information gained from a sensor configuration. Asymptotic approximations simplify the information gain as a scalar measure of the Fisher information matrix built from the sensitivities of the response QoI at the sensor locations with respect to the parameters to be inferred. For the case of inadequate data, information is also borrowed from the prior distribution of the parameters to be inferred. Based on asymptotic approximation, valid for large number of data, the expected utility function to be maximized is a scalar measure of the sensitivity of the responses at the measured locations with respect to the parameters to be inferred. A sensor configuration affects which response sensitivities are involved in the information gain measure. To take into account the model and input uncertainties, the expected information gain is introduced over all possible model and input uncertainties. The resulting multi-dimensional probability integrals are estimated using Monte Carlo sampling techniques. The heuristic FSSP algorithm is used to optimize the objective function. The large computational burden associated with the OSP designed to be robust to model and input uncertainties is also pointed out and remedies are provided to reduce the computational effort.

The proposed framework is validated using a 6 and a 20-DOF nonlinear spring-mass chain models with internal spring forces represented by hysteretic nonlinearities of the Bouc-Wen type. The effect of the model prediction and measurement error parameters, the size of the prior distribution, the various input characteristics (amplitude and frequency content) and the uncertain time history details of the excitation on the sensor placement is thoroughly studied and insightful interpretations have been made/reported. In particular, it is demonstrated that designing the OSP for a single realization of a stochastic input may suffice to obtain a very good design for the robust case that takes into account the uncertainty in the details of the stochastic input. For the specific application considered, the design of the optimal sensor configuration based on a specific realization of the stochastic excitation provides a near optimal solution and helps reduce the computational effort and excessive storage requirements.

The proposed OSP framework take into account in the sensor configuration design the structural and prediction error modeling uncertainties, as well as input uncertainties related to the details of the time history of the excitation and the characteristics of the spectrum of the excitation. The framework can also be extended to handle in the OSP design the variabilities in the location of the excitation sources (impact hammer applied at different positions of a structure) as well as the type of the excitation and excitation sources (impact hammer providing short impulse excitation signals versus electromechanical actuator providing broadband and other excitation signals). Besides the OSP demonstrated in this study, the framework can be used for optimal selection of the type (accelerations, strains, etc) and number of sensors for general linear and nonlinear systems. Although not demonstrated in this study, the method is directly applicable to the design of optimal sensor configurations involving mixed type of sensors such as placing optimally acceleration and strain sensors. The method can also be used to select the optimal number of sensors as the ones that provide a pre-selected high percentage of the maximum information that can be gained by fully populating the structure with sensors at all possible locations. Alternatively, since the information gain is an increasing function of the number of sensors, the optimal number of sensors can be formally obtained by simultaneously maximizing the information gain and minimizing the cost of instrumentation (sensor cost as well as sensor network installation and maintenance cost) [37].

6. Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764547.

Appendix A. Nonlinear Spring-Mass Chain Model

Appendix A.1. Formulation of Dynamic Equations of Motion

Let $q_i(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t)$ be the restoring force for the nonlinear link i , where $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, \dots, u_{\text{Ndof}}]^T$ and $\dot{\mathbf{u}} = [\dot{u}_1, \dots, \dot{u}_{\text{Ndof}}]^T$ are the displacement and velocity vectors, respectively, with components u_i and \dot{u}_i to be the relative displacement and velocity time histories of floor i with respect to the base. The restoring force vector $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t) = [q_1(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t), \dots, q_N(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t)]^T$ is given by

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{c} \circ (\tilde{\mathbf{L}}\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)) + \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k})(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{u}(t)) + \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{z}(t) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where \mathbf{c} is a vector related to damping values and \mathbf{k} is a vector containing the stiffness parameters of each floor. $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is a vector of the rigidity ratios (i.e. the ratio of final tangent stiffness k_{t_i} to initial stiffness k_i , with $(0 < \alpha < 1)$ and $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \mathbf{1}$ corresponds to linear system) and the i -th component z_i of the vector \mathbf{z} is the hysteresis displacement of each floor. Here the notation $\mathbf{a} \circ \mathbf{b}$ denotes the element-wise product of the vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , and $\tilde{\mathbf{L}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\text{Ndof} \times \text{Ndof}}$ is a lower triangular transformation matrix given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{L}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & & & & \\ -1 & 1 & & & \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & & \\ \vdots & \ddots & -1 & 1 & \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The nonlinearity is represented by Bouc-Wen hysteretic model given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{A} \circ (\mathbf{L}\dot{\mathbf{u}}) - \boldsymbol{\beta} \circ |\mathbf{L}\dot{\mathbf{u}}| \circ \mathbf{z} \circ |\mathbf{z}|^{\circ(\mathbf{n}-1)} - \boldsymbol{\gamma} \circ (\mathbf{L}\dot{\mathbf{u}}) \circ |\mathbf{z}|^{\circ \mathbf{n}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where for the link i the i -th component of the parameter vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{n} controls the hysteresis amplitude and the smoothness of the hysteretic curve respectively. Along with \mathbf{n} , the hysteretic parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ determine the basic shape of the hysteretic loop. Their sum or difference will define a hardening or softening relationship. Pinching effect, stiffness and strength degradation are neglected in this hysteresis formulation. Using the vector of restoring force $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t) \in \mathbb{R}^{\text{Ndof}}$, the equations of motion for the nonlinear system can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^T \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, t) = \mathbf{L}_f \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

and using Eq. (A.1), Eq. (A.4) can be rearranged as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^T \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k})\tilde{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{u}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^T \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{z}(t) = \mathbf{L}_f \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The system of equations of motion Eq. (A.5) can be solved by introducing the state space vector

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_1(t) \\ \mathbf{y}_2(t) \\ \mathbf{y}_3(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \\ \mathbf{z}(t) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

and deriving the state space form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{y}}_1(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{y}}_2(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{y}}_3(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_2(t) \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{y}_2(t) + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_1(t) + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{y}_3(t) \\ \mathbf{A} \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2(t)) - \boldsymbol{\beta} \circ |\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2(t)| \circ \mathbf{y}_3(t) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3(t)|^{n-1} - \boldsymbol{\gamma} \circ [\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2(t)] \circ |\mathbf{y}_3(t)|^n \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{f}(t) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where

$$\mathbf{f}(t) = \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{L}_f\mathbf{F}(t) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The equations of motion for a ground acceleration input $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g(t)$ are obtained by setting $\mathbf{L}_f\mathbf{F}(t) = -\mathbf{M}\mathbf{1}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g(t)$, leading to $\mathbf{f}(t) = \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{L}_f\mathbf{F}(t) = -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{M}\mathbf{1}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g(t) = -\mathbf{1}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g(t)$.

The nonlinear hysteretic part \mathbf{q}_{nl} of the restoring force \mathbf{q} is defined in matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{q}_{nl} = \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{y}_3 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Let $\mathbf{y}_{i\theta} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}_i(t)}{\partial \theta}$ be the sensitivity of the response $\mathbf{y}_i(t)$ with respect to a parameter θ , required in the optimal sensor placement formulation. Then the equations for the sensitivities are readily obtained by direct differentiation of Eq. (A.7) in the form:

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}_{1\theta} = \mathbf{y}_{2\theta} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{y}}_{2\theta} = & -\mathbf{M}_\theta^{-1}(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{y}_2 + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_1 + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_3) \\ & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{C}_\theta\mathbf{y}_2 + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{y}_{2\theta} + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\theta \circ \mathbf{k} + \boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k}_\theta)\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_1 + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_{1\theta} \\ & + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}(-\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\theta \circ \mathbf{k} + (\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k}_\theta)\mathbf{y}_3 + \mathbf{L}^T \text{diag}((\mathbf{1} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \circ \mathbf{k})\mathbf{y}_{3\theta}) + \mathbf{f}_\theta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{y}}_{3\theta} = & \mathbf{A}_\theta \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2) + \mathbf{A} \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_{2\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\beta}_\theta \circ |\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2| \circ \mathbf{y}_3 \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ(n-1)} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \circ \text{sign}(\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2) \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_{2\theta}) \circ \mathbf{y}_3 \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ(n-1)} \\ & - \boldsymbol{\beta} \circ |\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2| \circ \mathbf{n} \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ(n-1)} \mathbf{y}_{3\theta} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}_\theta \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ n} - \boldsymbol{\gamma} \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_{2\theta}) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ n} \\ & - \boldsymbol{\gamma} \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2) \circ \mathbf{n} \text{sign}(\mathbf{y}_3) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3|^{\circ(n-1)} \mathbf{y}_{3\theta} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \circ |\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2(t)| \circ \mathbf{y}_3(t) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3(t)|^{\circ(n-1)} \circ \log(|\mathbf{y}_3(t)|) \circ \mathbf{n}_\theta \\ & - \boldsymbol{\gamma} \circ (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{y}_2(t)) \circ |\mathbf{y}_3(t)|^{\circ n} \circ \log(|\mathbf{y}_3(t)|) \circ \mathbf{n}_\theta + \mathbf{0} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $\mathbf{f}_\theta(t) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(t)}{\partial \theta} = -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{M}_\theta\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{L}_f\mathbf{F}(t)$ for a general excitation, and $\mathbf{f}_\theta(t) = \mathbf{0}$ for a ground acceleration.

Appendix A.2. Implementation of Kanai-Tajimi Model

The Kanai-Tajimi filter is a commonly used model to represent the strong motion content and it is given as [57],

$$\ddot{u}_g = \ddot{x}_g + c w_t = -2\zeta_g \omega_g \dot{x}_g - \omega_g^2 x_g \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_g$ is the base acceleration, ω_g is the characteristic frequency of the soil layer, ζ_g is the damping ratio of the filter, c is the intensity of the white noise input, and w_t is a zero-mean Gaussian white noise input sequence, with sample at discrete time t following a Gaussian distribution $N(w_t|0, 1)$ of unit variance. The equation of motion of the filter can be written as,

$$\ddot{x}_g + 2\zeta_g \omega_g \dot{x}_g + \omega_g^2 x_g = -c w_t \quad (\text{A.14})$$

with $x_g(0) = \dot{x}_g(0) = 0$. Introducing the state vector

$$\begin{Bmatrix} y_4(t) \\ y_5(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} x_g(t) \\ \dot{x}_g(t) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

to augment the state vector in Eq. (A.6), the additional equations for the state vector Eq. (A.15) are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \dot{y}_4(t) \\ \dot{y}_5(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}_c \begin{Bmatrix} y_4(t) \\ y_5(t) \end{Bmatrix} - \mathbf{B}_c c w_t \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\omega_g^2 & -2\zeta_g\omega_g \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

and the forcing term in Eq. (A.7) takes the form $\mathbf{f}(t) = \mathbf{1}(2\zeta_g\omega_g y_5 + \omega_g^2 y_4)$. The sensitivity equations Eq. (A.10), Eq. (A.11) and Eq. (A.12) can be augmented by the equations

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \dot{y}_{4\theta} \\ \dot{y}_{5\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} y_{5\theta} \\ -2\zeta_g\omega_g y_{5\theta} - \omega_g^2 y_{4\theta} - 2(\zeta_{g\theta}\omega_g + \zeta_g\omega_{g\theta}) y_5 - 2\omega_g\omega_{g\theta} y_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

where the sensitivity of the forcing term in Eq. (A.7) is given by $\mathbf{f}_\theta(t) = \mathbf{1}[2\zeta_g\omega_g y_{5\theta} + \omega_g^2 y_{4\theta} + 2(\zeta_{g\theta}\omega_g + \zeta_g\omega_{g\theta}) y_5 + 2\omega_g\omega_{g\theta} y_4]$.

In the analysis, for a fair comparison of the utilities, the intensity of filtered input is kept the same for different values of uncertain filtered parameters ω_g and ζ_g . This is accomplished by selecting the value of the white noise input intensity c . Specifically, using a discrete state space representation of the Kanai-Tajimi model Eq. (A.14), applying the Liapunov equation, and assuming a scalar stationary zero-mean Gaussian white noise excitation with variance $\sigma_{wn}^2 = c^2$, the variance of the ground motion acceleration is given by

$$\sigma_{\ddot{u}_g}^2 = c^2(\mathbf{G}\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_x\mathbf{G}^T + \mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^T) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_x$ can be obtained by solving the discrete Liapunov equation

$$\mathbf{A}\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_x\mathbf{A}^T - \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_x + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^T = 0 \quad (\text{A.20})$$

with the discrete state space matrices given, using zero-order hold, as $\mathbf{A} = \exp(\mathbf{A}_c\Delta t)$ and $\mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{I})\mathbf{A}_c^{-1}\mathbf{B}_c$, and Δt is the sampling time, and $\mathbf{G} = [-\omega_g^2 \quad -2\zeta_g\omega_g]$. Given the intensity $\sigma_{\ddot{u}_g}$ of the excitation and the filter parameters ω_g and ζ_g , the intensity c of the white noise input is computed from Eq. (A.19).

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